

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

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Initial networking report

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1. The WYRED Network

Since November 2016 (Month1 - M1) and the kick off meeting of the Consortium in Salamanca (Spain), the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) has set high standards and allocated one of its biggest interests into the creation of a strong and growing Network in order to reach more people from diverse backgrounds with different experiences and knowledge. These people/target groups, as the projects foresees, primarily are children and young people who will, by engaging in the process, will get to know better, identify and interact with other stakeholders at policy level and wider society. By involving these diverse groups, WYRED Network tries to connect them and create the space for engagement, collaboration and discussion (Durán-Escudero, García-Peñalvo, & Therón-Sánchez, 2017; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017). In the process of engaging children, young people and stakeholders, the project has set various means to reach out to them and at the same time assure that it includes as many target groups and people as possible.

In order to understand the importance of growing a strong network for WYRED, in this report we will present the steps and methods implemented and at the same time try to visualize the outreach and background of people engaged until this point. As defined by WYRED project proposal, the aim is to engage children and young people and offer the opportunity to contribute and proceed to the formulation and execution of the research which will take place in Working Package 6 (WP6). Therefore, Working Package 4 (WP4) aims to bringing children, youngsters and other stakeholders on-board and building strong basis through a diverse and active network at the beginning of each cycle. As from Month 1 (M1), the focus was to bring together various and different stakeholders from across Europe connecting different levels in a local, regional and international context and therefore foster engagement and assist in creation and dissemination of stronger outcomes and/or results.

“The eventual sustainability of WYRED and the success of the first and second cycles of WYRED activity depend to a large extent on achieving a sufficient critical mass of participants from diverse backgrounds.” Having this part of the application in mind, the consortium has worked on various ways and means that could attract and engage high number of stakeholders, beyond the minimum numbers expected and set by the WPs and the application. The diversity and experience of each partner was the key factor in reaching out to as many children, young people and other stakeholders as possible in each phase. Not all have always succeeded, but as the Network develops so does the expertise of the Consortium. Therefore, the organizational background, but also the learning taking place from each phase and process, can assure the growth of the Network and therefore the sustainability of the project.

2. First Phase of Networking

While acknowledging that Networking is an ongoing process, especially in this type of projects, the consortium feels that it is vital to be aware of the importance of processes of the WYRED Network in the initiating phase.

This report collects the results of the actions carried out during the period between the two transnational project meetings, from M1 to M7 (Tasks 4.1-4.5, as described in the Work Package 4 description) and provides a set of final recommendations based on the lesson learned to guide the partnership in the implementation of the second iteration of the WYRED cycle.

2.1 The Networking Process

The networking process included the creation of the WYRED Manifesto (Task 4.1), the design of the project logo and slogan (Task 4.2), the creation of a promotional video (Task 4.3), the Initial stakeholders contact (Task 4.4) and then the implementation of a Delphi - Survey (Tasks 4.5), considered as a set of preliminary activities before moving in M7-M8 to WP5 Social Dialogues. Each phase had a specific purpose and worked as a following step to the inclusion and engagement of children, young people and other stakeholders. As a ladder that the project and partners follow, it created a continuation of activities that were used to create the image, inform, engage and define WYRED. Creating a Network requires effort and it is very demanding. The workflow had to be in line and that was the point when WYRED required fully the experience of each partner, but also of other Networks they are part of. In each step, this diversity of backgrounds was to be used appropriately in order to build this Network and assure that it becomes strong and keeps growing in each phase to come.

From the beginning of the project, the building of the Network started with setting our position as WYRED. The definition and the outreach is well connected. As defined in the project proposal, the Consortium worked on the creation of [two Manifestos](#) that made the WYRED comprehensible and closer to potential participants. Moving on in parallel, the Networking has been set to start in Month 2 (M2) at local and regional level with the initial stakeholders' contact as partners started "spreading the word" and creating links with communities. These links were important as WYRED moved towards specific approaches that could engage children, young people and other stakeholders and actually map their heterogeneity and interests. As the project combines and interconnects every process, in M5 the Consortium implemented the Stakeholders Questionnaire which was the first step of mapping the Stakeholders interested in getting involved, but also setting key themes of discussion and interest.

The results and contacts created and collected by the Questionnaire, were the force and material that contributed to further engagement and analysis for the preparation and implementation of the 1st Delphi Process taking place in M6. As we talk about a project that focuses on engaging young people, it is important to use their terminology and channels of communication. Therefore, from M5, WYRED initiated a Slogan

competition which was an opportunity for young people to share their ideas on what the project is and should be about and, in parallel, worked on the WYRED promotional video.

As the initial part, the Networking process was set to create the basis that WYRED will stand on. Through the objectives that the project has set in this process and Working Package (WP4), there were 4 equally important phases that were of highest value - different in their format, however linked around a common purpose to inform, engage and create the framework that our work is based on. Each step was set to build on the work performed by the previous and therefore create a Network that can grow and develop, be sustainable and allow engagement, cooperation and representation.

2.2 Objectives

The WYRED project and in this specific case the Networking process aims in bringing together children, young people, other stakeholders and policy makers from around Europe. That means that certain processes should be implemented in order to reach the objectives of the Networking Process:

- **Build synergies and include a variety of different constituencies of stakeholders (including children and young people);**
- **Include and engage a sufficient critical mass of participants from diverse backgrounds - in line with Working Package 2 (WP2) on Inclusion and Diversity;**
- **Initiate the process of dialogue in the project and foster engagement for further processes like Social Dialogue (WP5);**

- **Identify the key themes that concern children and young people in relation to future social change and prepare for future activities of WYRED cycle;**
- **Attract participants through the process, that can engage on ongoing and future processes of WYRED project.**

Each objective connects to a specific phase or set of processes that are expected to be applied in every WYRED Cycle, through the lifetime of the project. The objective of engagement and participation is a matter that WP4 highly focuses on. In the process of building of the Network, WYRED is bringing together stakeholders from a variety of different constituencies such as research and policy, children and young people, schools, youth organisations and others across Europe. In order to reach out to as many stakeholders as possible partners were spreading the information directly or using the platforms such as European Youth Forum, Social Platform, Lifelong Learning Platform etc.

Objective of building synergies and including stakeholders connects to the planning and background of the consortium. Each partner involved in the project (in particular OXFAM, YEU, PYE Global and EARLY YEARS), has a different structure and focus on specific target groups and therefore bringing international, regional, national and local connections and ensuring their engagement.

Aiming at engagement of the stakeholders and policy makers means also creation of sustainable network that can generate greater impact and success to and by the project and its cycles. This does not refer only to the number reached, but more importantly to the diversity and continuation of engagement of those involved. In order to assure diversity, WYRED has consortium strong in terms of its access to children, young people and other participants, while applying diversity criteria.

Phases of WP4 - creation of a manifesto and project visual identity, an initial contact, a questionnaire and then the implementation of a Delphi Survey - are all designed to support reaching out to stakeholders. Parallel, in order to maximize and assure the quality of engagement through the project's phases, the working package also included the creation of logo, a slogan completion, a video and training for participants taking place in close collaboration of all partners.

Another WYRED objective is to initiate the dialogue process in the project, by identifying the key themes that concern children and young people in relation to desired social change. By using Questionnaire and Survey, WYRED was fostering engagement and collecting information in order to identify the key themes, but also set the data that assist in preparing for the subsequent activity in the WYRED cycle and also to attract more participants towards WYRED. In each phase, the diversity of people and freedom to express themselves had to be assured and used properly in order to map and prioritise key themes that WYRED will set its work and focus on. With the support of the work taking place in Work Package 2 (Inclusion), Networking tried to focus on ***“an understanding of diversity that regards differences as normal and values the idea of equal participation in all***

aspects of life and decision making¹” and setting *“inclusion criteria ...oriented towards the well-known diversity factors gender, age, education respectively work situation, socio-economic status, cultural background/migration, regionality, disabilities and religion.²”*

Still pending element of the WP4 is the Online Trainings. The Online trainings aim at enhancing the understanding of WYRED and its potential, tackling matters of data privacy and ethics before taking part and engaging in online WYRED platform and its communities. Based on the diversity and heterogeneity of the target groups, the consortium has decided to create different approaches for age groups.

As discussed within the consortium, each video will tackle 4 different groups. First, facilitators and parents in relevance to the engagement of children, second the under 18 users, the young people above 18 and then other stakeholders.

Each WP4 phase has, until this moment, set the grounds for achieving each one of the objectives set for WYRED. Understanding the networking as an ongoing process, we are expecting to continue spreading the WYRED network and increasing the participation of all relevant stakeholders.

3. Outcomes and Results of WP4

As listed above, the WP4 and its purpose to build a strong sustainable Network included 4 engaging phases. These phases (initial contact, stakeholders’ questionnaire, Delphi study and slogan competition) were the basis of the WYRED project and their outcomes were and are used as the main force and material that supports other processes, such as Social Dialogues (WP5). Acknowledging the work done, it shows to the partnership the need to keep up and grow an engaging and sustainable Network. The networking factor does not end and should not end within Working Package 4 (WP4) and it is clear that it has its own importance in every other process and Working Packages of the project. In the following sections, a description of each engaging phase is provided. The last section is devoted to the two main pillars of the project visual identity: project logo and promotional video.

3.1 Initial Contact

From M1 and after setting the common understanding within the consortium, the WYRED project was taking form and coming to life. However, in order to assure its healthy functioning, it had to ensure bringing people on board who would be able and interested to engage in it, shape it and set the direction that the process would take. That meant to share the existence of the project and be able to engage people from the very beginning.

¹ WYRED Handbook, Inclusion Processes (WP2), Sabine Zauchner-Studnicka, MOVES, 2017

² WYRED Handbook, Inclusion Processes (WP2), Sabine Zauchner-Studnicka, MOVES, 2017

That was the first and most vital part of the Networking and in order to achieve that the consortium used its' contacts as a base to grow. This base that had to be well created in order to assure more engagement and allow more impact in each step and process of the first months of WYRED.

Based on various ideas and practices, in combination to the WYRED visual identity (logo, templates etc.), each partner used different tools, as presented during collection of data by each partner, that would be suitable for the initial contact.

With the use of different tools, consortium has created common approach in order to present WYRED and collect opinions and perspectives in relevance to the future of WYRED – presentations and/or specific questions and themes of discussion (e.g. MOVES presentation on WYRED³, WYRED Interviews and the set of questions⁴).

Gathering information from partners' reports collected in M7, we can identify that the media used for contacting the target groups were in their format diverse and tailored to each specific case. At the same time, the ongoing Valorisation and Dissemination process were about to set the online presence of the project so the “offline” and “online” space could co-exist and at the same time support each other. Within the framework of Initial Contact and with constant coordination and communication, the consortium allocated its focus on the closest sphere of influence which was their local communities and partners.

Looking at the reporting of each partner from M1 to M4 and based on a contact list and data that each partner shared, we see that the consortium separated the target groups (TG) into 4 different types.

TG1 CHILDREN, YOUNG PEOPLE, YOUTH ORGANIZATION AND PLATFORMS

TG2 EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

TG3 POLICY AND DECISION MAKERS

TG4 OPINION MAKERS

The numbers reached within this phase - “Initial Contact” - are presented by the partners with the use of 3 different reporting methods: interview reports, contact list⁵ and networking data collection. As set by the contact list and approached as a first contact by each partner, the consortium reached:

- **36 Youth Organizations and Platforms (which gather approximately 150 international youth organizations and national youth councils);**
- **92 Education Institutions;**

³ Sabine Zauchner-Studnicka, MOVES, 2017

⁴ WYRED project Consortium, M3/M4, 2017

⁵ “Valorisation Plan - contact data base”, WP 8 - Deliverable 8.1, OXFAM ITALY, 2017

- **11 Policy Makers;**
- **12 Opinion Makers**

Combining and analysing the information provided by each partner through the networking data collection for the initial contacts, we see that the consortium has directly approached:

- **73 Youth Organizations and Platforms;**
- **56 Education Institutions;**
- **2 Policy Makers;**
- **1 Opinion Maker**

At the same time, some of these contacts were strategically approached as they are Networks or platforms, therefore allowing to WYRED a further reach out to relevant stakeholders. To be more precise, the Consortium used contacts like Teen Yoga Foundation network (estimated 350 Members), European Youth Forum (104 members) or Lifelong Learning Platform (41 Members) which within their structures disseminated and shared information on WYRED and giving the option to engage and participate in WYRED and its' processes.

Observing the preparation and the outreach of the Initial Contact, we see that the motivation was to promote the project and its objectives to as many beneficiaries as possible and therefore giving better chances for participation and engagement to following phases and processes. Nevertheless, beyond the numbers, it is important to see the main tools used as listed from what the partners reported (in order of most used to least used):

- **Emails and/or Mail “with project abstracts”;**
- **Face to Face meetings (Sessions, Presentations, Interviews);**
- **Phone calls and/or Skype calls**
- **Workshops and events of partners**

The Face to Face meeting and workshops involved discussions and presentations on:

- **WYRED theme** “The young people have a key role in our society, but they are not well represented and their voices are unheard, and this makes it hard for research and policy to identify and understand their needs.”
- **WYRED Project** - “The WYRED project aims to create a framework for dialogue and research in which children and young people can express and explore the key issues that they see as important in relation to digital society. Process, Phases, Timeline and Cycles.
- **Similar Examples that could foster understanding the Project** - Using material from Project proposal (e.g. Working Package 6);
- **WYRED Website;**
- **Slogan Competition Process and Call;**
- **Process of the Dialogue Phase and description of Working Package;**
- **Idea behind the creation of the Platform that WYRED will use.**

The topics, based on the reporting on interviews, were:

- **Manifestos;**
- **The project, the process and its’ impact;**
- **Challenges and Opportunities;**
- **Suitable age of participants;**
- **Heterogeneity/Diversity of Participants;**
- **WYRED and most important topics to tackle;**
- **Availability of Young people;**
- **Questions to tackle during upcoming phases (e.g. Delphi);**
- **Benefits, contributions and suggestions.**

As observed in available data from following processes, such as “Joining the Community” in Stakeholders Questionnaire, we get to see further engagement by Stakeholders initially contacted. Some examples are Lifelong Learning Platform (BE), Mind Body Yoga (UK) etc. The use of creating initial contacts was the kicking off point to disseminate information about the project and engage people, but also at the same time to prepare the setup of the WYRED Community that would allow to the project to function and become sustainable.

3.2 Stakeholders’ Questionnaire

Based on the initial contact phase and the work performed by the consortium the second phase had good grounds set to be developed. As foreseen by the project proposal, at the end of M3 to the beginning of M4, the consortium started preparing the Stakeholders’ questionnaire (WYRED Consortium, 2017), which would be the first tangible process engaging people in WYRED, but also the phase that would provide data on the Delphi study and provide information on the subject areas that Social Dialogues would cover.

The consortium emphasised that involvement of children and young people shall be done with them as equal stakeholders as any other ones during the whole process.

The questionnaire has been structured in order to server as the starting point of engaging stakeholders in WYRED process and as basis for next phases (Delphi and Social Dialogues). The aim was to lead the responder from general topics to more specific issues and to detailed research questions. As set by partners, the items used as examples were based on the experiences with the stakeholder meetings during the initial contact phase. As the platform was not yet done the consortium, decided to implement the process through a [Google Form](#) and disseminate the information through the [website](#), emails and messages partners and initial contacts, but also by using other media of partners as you can see below. The Questionnaire was open from 21st of March till the 8th of April 2017.

Good afternoon dear CYC office,

Based on our cooperation and experiences together, I am contacting you on behalf of [Youth for Exchange and Understanding](#) to inform you about an ongoing project that I strongly believe you could support us with and additionally to ask you to help us to disseminate a questionnaire with your members and partners and therefore offer the chance to more young people to have a say and get engaged.

As part of WYRED process, YEU and other consortium members have created a questionnaire to assist us during the process. Therefore, I would kindly ask you to fill up and share our questionnaire with your members.

For more information, please also check our manifesto.

If possible, please share the following message:

[YEU](#) is part of an ongoing Horizon2020 project and is calling for more stakeholders to be involved. As part of the process we want to engage more people and bring them on board to take part, collaborate and work on with us in relevance to the WYRED process.

The young have a key role to play in our society. They are frequently the drivers of new behaviours and understandings, and since they are part of the future society their views and perceptions should be taken into account. However, they are not well represented and their voices are unheard, and this makes it hard for research and policy to identify and understand their needs.

WYRED will create a framework for dialogue and research in which children and young people can express and explore the key issues that they see as important. The aim is to give young people a voice and provide platform from which they can communicate their perspectives to others. These others include **teachers, parents, other young people and especially decision makers who can inform policy, particularly in relation to children and young people's needs in relation to digital society.**

One central aim of WYRED is to take into account the perspectives of a broad variety of stakeholders from the very start of the project. We therefore ask all our stakeholders to share with us, in this short questionnaire, their views on what is important for todays' children and youth.

The questionnaire is available in the partner countries' languages.

Choose the language and click on the link to access the questionnaire: [EN](#), [DE](#), [ES](#), [HE](#), [IT](#), [TK](#).

Deadline is 06 of April 2017.

Thank you for your collaboration!

For more information related to the project, please check our [website](#).

Best regards,
Panagiotis Chatzimichail
Policy Officer
Youth for Exchange and Understanding International

Example of an Email sent to a Youth Council, calling for their contribution and dissemination to members and young people.

Dissemination of the process by LLLP (Platform of 34 members) which was an Initial Contact and has since then been engaged in all Networking phases. (30/04/2017)

Dissemination of the process by European Youth Forum (Platform of 104 members) which was an Initial Contact and has since then been engaged in all Networking phases.

Connecting the discussions and outcomes of the Initial Contact phase, the Stakeholders' Questionnaire process was to create connections and give more ownership to people who engaged as responders. As agreed within consortium and defined within the project, each partner had to reach a minimum of 50 responders while assuring diversity (demographic background of people and organizations)

WYRED slowly started implementing some diversity criteria (but not yet in depth e.g. level of education or socioeconomic background) and identifying the audience which it wished to engage. An interesting example is defining the gender of the participants, while offering the possibility of no answer or selecting "Other" as an option. This approach was not applied in all countries and questionnaires as there were local realities to be taken into consideration. As partners explained, cultural attitudes, perspectives and local approaches could have had a negative impact on participation and dissemination of the questionnaire by other organizations who could "question" the choice of Other. An example was Turkey and the dissemination of the Questionnaire in schools.

As presented in the Report on Stakeholders' Questionnaire, demographics of participants were:

Figure 1: Age of participants (Source: Moves, 2017)

Figure 2: Gender of participants (Source: Moves, 2017)

Figure 3: Profession of participants (Source: Moves, 2017)

Covering demographics and a certain set of diversity criteria, we move to the main and most important part. In order to derive data in relevance to the topics of Delphi Survey and to the work foreseen in Social Dialogues, we started setting the topics with the responders and observing their interests and perception as to what is important and/or neglected. Below you can see the set of questions and answers as presented from the final report on Stakeholders' Questionnaire⁶.

- A) In your view, which three of these topics are most important for children and young people today?
 Please add others if you think they should be included in your 3 most important issues. (Checklist)**

⁶ Sabine Zauchner-Studnicka, MOVES, 2017

Figure 4: Most important topics identified (Source: Moves, 2017)

Other topics per Country:

- Austria: Pop Culture/ Self-Reflection/ Empathy and Socially Acting
- Israel: Housing/ Leisure Time
- Turkey: Human, Animal and Environmental Rights/ Innovative education/ inadequacy of scientific education
- English Speaking Countries/Regions (Europe, U.K and Northern Ireland): Critical Thinking (Assessing Information), Gender Equality

B) Here is a selection of some specific issues that people see as relevant for children and young people today. Which three do you see as most important? Please add others if you think they should be included in your 3 most important issues.

Figure 5: Most important issues identified (Source: Moves, 2017)

Other issues per Country:

- Israel: Skills of Choice and decision making/Various instructional Films/ Coping with uncertain future/ Military Services
- Spain: Employment/ Entertainment/ Social Media

C) According to your experiences, what are the most neglected issues (by government and/or the media) that affect children and young people today?

Figure 6: Neglected issues identified (Source: Moves, 2017)

Figure 7: Other neglected issues identified (Source: Moves, 2017)

D) In the WYRED project, children and young people are going to explore specific questions relating to social issues. Here are some examples. Which in your view are the three most important?

Figure 8: Most important social issues identified (Source: Moves, 2017)

E) Other questions per Country:

- Austria:
 - What is addiction and how can I prevent it?
 - How can I save my privacy?
- Israel:
 - How can new Technologies change my life and the society?
 - Taking responsibility - how I take responsibility for my actions in all areas of life and an emphasis on digital space?
 - What are the stereotypes of people in my society and my world?
 - Expanding the stereotypes issue: increased exclusion of women in the public sphere, and legitimacy of expressing a variety of opinions.
- Spain:
 - What is the difference between sexual identity and sexual orientation?
- English Speaking Countries/Regions (Europe, U.K and Northern Ireland):
 - How to challenge and overcome Social Exclusion?
- Italy:
 - Is the society not based only on monetary values still possible?
 - What happens with information that we publish in internet?
 - How to use a cultural heritage in inclusion processes of immigrant population?

Taking a look at the questions given and to the path that the questionnaire follows, we get to see the responders' perspective regarding the topics that WYRED has selected based on initial discussions. Analysing the responds properly, even if it took a lot of efforts to bring the data into a form that can be analysed, we could identify Key Themes which we would build on. Based on the responders' positions on topics and collecting more information we could go further with the Delphi Survey and therefore have the Key Themes set for discussion. Parallel to the process of having more detailed and in-depth topics and Key Themes, we used the Stakeholders Questionnaire as a change to engage further. As mentioned before, in order to build feeling of ownership to people participating in this phase, we also used an extra section to allow more people to join WYRED and grow the network by using "Join the WYRED Community".

"Join the WYRED Community" was the second section of the Google Form used, which allow responders to "register" as members of the Community and therefore be able to participate and get informed in following phases of the project. The invitation message as seen below, was set to bring entities on-board if they shared the belief of in empowering and engaging young people.

"WYRED believes in empowering young people, and giving them a voice. If you share this belief with us, then join us! Help young people to explore the issues that are important to them.

Join the WYRED community!

If you are interested in joining the WYRED community, please fill in the following demographic data and we will get in touch with you as soon as possible.

This section was giving the option to interested members to provide information on the Organization (Name, Area of Activity), ability to check their work and possibilities for cooperation (Website and Country) and then setting a link with a Contact person (position, email). Based on the registration offered, as seen bellow, the Stakeholders Questionnaire was a chance to engage several types of organizations in a variety of countries outside of the Consortium.

Countries involved in the Questionnaire:

European Union		Europe		Non-Europe
- Austria	- Lithuania	- Azerbaijan	- Ukraine	- Canada
- Belgium	- Netherlands	- Bosnia & Herzegovina		- Israel
- Cyprus	- Portugal	- FYROM/Macedonia		- Morocco
- Estonia	- Romania	- Montenegro		- Tunisia
- Greece	- Spain	- Serbia		
- Ireland	- UK (SCT, EN, NIR)	- Turkey		
- Italy				

Types of Organizations registered, based on area of Activity:

Going through the process of creating, implementing and analysing the Questionnaire we get to see that this step was an important contribution to our process. As a tool to engage relevant target groups, even if expected numbers were not reached, it still offered a chance to initiate ownership and expand the Network. By creating new contacts and involving variety of Stakeholders, we have set a deeper analysis in defining the Key Themes that were necessary to proceed in following stages. At the same time, building up the image of WYRED community, we initiated a Network that could give us access in engaging more young people and stakeholders from different backgrounds, beyond geographical barriers and a chance to reach out to marginalized groups of young people.

3.3 Delphi study

The main objective of the Delphi study in WYRED was to identify and prioritize key areas of interest for young persons (to be explored further in the subsequent activities of the project), and to provide additional insights regarding the involvement of young people in decision making related to their concerns, attitudes and perceptions.

The Delphi method is widely used in different areas, for the elicitation of experts' opinions on a certain subject, by means of an iterative anonymous group interaction. It involves repeated (multi-round) polling of individuals, in each round feeding back anonymized responses from earlier rounds. The idea is that such a process allows for better judgements to be made without undue influence from certain "dominant" individuals.

The WYRED Delphi study consisted of two online surveys: one aimed at young people and one aimed at stakeholders. For each survey, different questionnaires were developed for the first and for the second round. The first round consisted of one closed question (rating the most important issues of concern for young people) and additional open questions dealing with ways of engaging young people in decision making and the benefit to society of such engagement. The second round consisted of closed questions formulated based on the results obtained in the first round.

The questionnaires were accessible online, in six languages, according to the WYRED partner countries: English, Spanish, German, Italian, Hebrew and Turkish. For privacy protection, each invitee received a personal code to be inserted in the online form while filling-in the questionnaire.

206 young people and 69 stakeholders participated in the first round. 260 young people and 89 stakeholders participated in the second round.

Detailed description, results and analysis of the Delphi are presented in a separate WYRED report entitled "[WYRED Delphi Study - Results Report](#)" dated July 7, 2017.

The results of the Delphi study provide valuable inputs to the subsequent social dialogues in which these issues will be explored further in detail.

3.4 Slogan Competition

Moving on to the last, but equally important phase of the Networking WP, we get to see further dissemination of project information and a chance for further engagement of more young people in this diverse and sustainable Network of WYRED. The Slogan Competition preparation and implementation was a long process, but a vital one as we had to assure correct framework that would allow participation, understanding and opportunities while at the same time fostering engagement and connection to WYRED. The framework had to be changed and adopted. As other timeframes and processes had to be as well modified according to the needs of the audience and to the possibilities that the project had at the current time, the Slogan process had certain changes until we have reached the final format that we get to see today.

As the framework around the use of Slogan was yet to be fully decided (from initial idea to have one slogan, now we have three), the involved partners had to adjust the format of the implementation process. Initially the idea was to include the creation of Slogan in the Trainings and processes involving young people. Due to dates and also need to have enough time for participants to create and submit proposals, the Consortium decided to make it simpler. Based on the available tools, experience and feedback of the Consortium, it was decided that the [Slogan Competition](#) would be done as a call, allowing submission of proposals separated in age groups. By separating the slogan process into three age groups, a fair competition was allowed but also a bigger outreach towards different age groups. At the same time, that meant having three slogans, that the Consortium needs to reflect on how to use them properly as expected and defined by the call. The tool used to collect the proposals was [Google Form](#) or for videos and images by email at info@wyredproject.eu by the 28th of April 2017. The final selection, as planned, was done at the last meeting (May 2017), based on a voting by the consortium per Group.

Based on the Call and the applications received (270), the results per group are as presented below:

Figure 9: Slogan competition results per age group (Oxfam, 2017)

Networking Report
WP4_D4.3

During the second partners meeting final decision on the winner of each group has been made and the results were disseminated through the [WYRED website](#). Below you can see the announcement of winners and the actual slogans selected by the Consortium.

You GoT WYRED!

270 slogan's proposals have been submitted

From Turkey, Northern Ireland, Austria, Italy, Spain, Georgia and Cyprus

And

We are glad to announce that ~~The~~ Winners are

Under 14

Share your dream - be part of the WYRED team: Vincent Lowry - Saint Macarten's Youth Club - Northern Ireland

14-17

Raise Your Voice, Be Your Own Future: Elif Çalışkan - Acarkent Doğa IB World School - Turkey

over 17

Be part, not apart: David Furtschegger – University of Innsbruck - Austria

The selection was based on the message, the content and the rhyme of each slogan

Winning students will be contacted in order to get their prize

Thank you!

The WYRED team

3.5 Project logo and promotional video

Creating a logo for a research project is different to creating a logo for a commercial product, since each of the people involved has different understandings of what is involved in the project, and different perceptions of what constitutes successful visual communication, largely based on their own visual taste and history.

An important issue is the intended function of the logo. Some are designed simply to grab the attention, others aim to communicate an idea through the image, others are more focused on creating an

identity that will be memorable and recognizable. For example, logos like the F of Facebook, or that of the BBC, are not immediately transparent, they are however recognizable, possibly due to their simplicity.

In our view, the most important role of the logo in WYRED relates to identity. WYRED will not be presented through its logo, rather the logo will serve as a memorable image that comes to be associated with the project. That said, the image should resonate with the key concepts of the project.

Concepts:

The WYRED project involves a wide range of ideas and concepts, and a basic principle of the project is that it is open-ended. We are creating a site for conversations and research, but it is not clear until those processes begin what the focus, or areas of focus, may turn out to be.

However, some general notions can be identified. A central concept is the notion of the “digital” world or society, which is implied by the name of the project. Others related to this include connection, networks and change.

Another group of concepts related to communication. Ideas like dialogue, expression, voice and conversation are included in this group.

Others related to the social and political dimensions of the work. Here terms like identity, diversity, inclusion and freedom were central but also words relating to the groups involved, children and young people, and youth.

The last key group of concepts related to knowledge and discovery. Terms like exploration, research, inspiration, the brain and inquiry were important.

Clearly, not all the concepts involved can be captured within a single logo.

After discussion at that meeting, the key concepts which were to be expressed through the logo were narrowed down to **YOUTH** and **VOICE**.

WYRED project - Young people should have a voice

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5DE07H_vDe8

Video objectives:

In order to get the children and the young people interested in the WYRED project and engaging them to participate in it, it is important to explain them the main WYRED question - how exists a lack of a real perspective that society has on the youth - and a possible solution - if the WYRED project and the youth starts working together we can shape the society we live in.

Target group:

The principal audience is children and young people, since the main objective is to attract this group to the project, and contribute to the project visibility among this target group. However, the second group, adults who work with young people is also valuable since they may function as recommenders of the project, and the video can raise awareness among them.

Main message:

The main message we want to transmit in WYRED video is based on the WYRED manifestos. The central idea is that society lacks appropriate perspectives on youth, relying on stereotypes of what young people are and what they think. They are treated as a homogenous group, ignoring the particularities of individuals and groups, their

voices are not listened to, and research to explore their needs fails to engage with what is relevant to them. Consequently, there is a misperception of the reality of what is to be a young person in today's society.

Because of this, there is a need to find ways to give a voice to young people so that they can voice their concerns, explore them together and as a result generate ideas and suggestions that can shape the society we live in. Society needs to hear and include the concerns of young people and the WYRED project aims to help this happen. If we want a perspective based on young people's realities, we need to hear it from them.

Metaphoric view technique:

The Metaphoric view technique is based in the figure of speech used in literature in which a word or phrase literally denoting one kind of object or idea is used in place of another to suggest a likeness or analogy between them. Therefore, this technique consists in the translation of the meaning of one idea or concept in to an object, creating a more visual and attractive effect, making the message more immediate and arresting.

The idea was to create a video in which with the help of footage of real objects the basic ideas of WYRED are explained. We decided to use the following metaphors:

- **The balloons** are the "main protagonist" of this video, because they represent the different voices of the youth. We have decided to use this object because of its malleability and the wide range of possibilities to play with it. We can use different colors, shapes, movements...
- **The light and the darkness** will symbolize the understanding or misunderstanding of these voices.
- **Window** explains that there is an option, a way to be heard.
- **Outdoor** symbolize the understanding

4. Recommendations

- a) The network is consisted by net and work. In order to keep this net strong and well tied we need to work constantly for and in it. There is no ending of this process and it should be understood as such. Each moment is a moment to net-work.
- b) The process of the initial contact phase has given a lot of ideas, and has built an understanding of who (audiences), what (needs) and how (channels of communication). In order to keep the network alive, we need to keep our who/what/how always in mind.
- c) The identification of strengths and weaknesses of each contact will allow WYRED to be more efficient and better connected to its Network. Evaluating quality, expertise and time (deadlines) is necessary to be aware of needed adjustments and compromising when engaging our targeted audiences in the future.
- d) Carefully plan the timeline – having in mind deadlines set by the project proposal, avoid overlap with other events and/or holidays especially those connected to children and youth people (school schedules, for example). Proper and honest timing reflect also the way how Network functions.

- e) Realities and timeframes of our audiences and people we want to engage should be our reality, rather sticking up to processes and timelines that in the end can affect engagement and impact. We need to adjust to them and their schedules as we need them to engage and be productive.
- f) Assure data protection and privacy at any points. Obligated or requested, you need to provide safe space to your network as it is the core of the project, but also what will keep the outreach and impact alive. Moments of uncertainty are moments that people tend to move away.
- g) No need for repetition of phases and processes as we have “tested” the ground and now we are aware of the proper way of implementation. Avoid similar processes, like several surveys (Stakeholders’ vs Delphi) that could create frustration, confusion and ending up with a negative impact on the network.
- h) Use the power of meeting people and putting actual faces in front of WYRED. The most engaging processes were the ones we were present, as we had a chance to create links and put people behind contexts and phases.
- i) Be aware of processes and implementation phases of WYRED. Use the time, preferably, just before we implement an action to actually approach people and engage them. The “waiting time” is always against us as people forget or they move on with different priorities and obligations.
- j) Evaluate constantly strengths and weaknesses of the partnership and their contact points. Each partner has different powers when it comes to networking. Be aware and don’t forget these powers. They are always necessary to keep a good network together.
- k) The strongest part of the Network is the first team which initiated it. Clarity, continuous in-depth explanation and support, learning from mistakes, consulting and collaborating can assure a strong core. Don’t only build a strong network around something that is not yet strong from within.
- l) Similar networks are important to the WYRED Network and creation of synergies. Bring similar projects on board, invite your networks, member organizations and partners to support, engage and contribute at any possible moment. You can be surprised about the impact.
- m) Compromising is necessary but be aware of procedures and always have in mind the important of quality. Quality is above any timeframe, tool or person. Avoid repetition of mistakes and always reflect on quality before taking a decision. Be sure of your proposals and be aware of your initiatives as your network will reflect on it. When a process is affected at the same time it affects the network.
- n) Young people are not homogeneous, therefore don’t treat them as such. Assure diversity of options, possibilities and accessibility. From backgrounds and age to capacities, their engagement is a vital part for WYRED.

- o) Use your events at all levels to talk about this network and WYRED. This is not just a project of yours. This is something that people out of WYRED team started investing in a project that can engage not for the sake of numbers, but for its expected impact and results.
- p) Learn from others when it comes to empowering the network. Each level has its own method. Use your partners' experience to have a greater impact on the people around you. Use your experience to empower your partners to do the same with people around them.

5. Conclusions

During the first 7 months of the WYRED project, there has been an important outreach towards children, young people and other stakeholders and their active engagement. The initiation of a network is not an easy task, starting from rethinking all the processes foreseen by the project proposal and facing the reality check to involving stakeholders in shaping the process of WYRED and having their voices heard, especially those of children and young people.

From the early stages, WYRED project got stakeholders coming from variety of backgrounds involved, following the principle of heterogeneity of children and young people rather than usual homogenous approach to these groups.

WYRED has created tendency from the early beginning to have an open, reflective and critical approach when working with target groups which makes it more difficult for realization but nothing else than true and genuine as it reflects the position, opinions and attitudes of children and young people today all over Europe.

There are some practices and processes that we need to reconsider and not repeat same paths and mistakes (less surveys repetition for example) which will make WYRED network easier to be built with more feedback and involvement from stakeholders.

From M1 to M7, we focused on engaging beneficiaries and building a network with them, while from this point and on we need to ensure Network's power and existence and continue growing what the consortium as core team of the project has started - as individuals, consortium and project. A strong network means strong impact and outreach.

6. References

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